

Sketch Classification with Convolutional Neural Networks

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Abstract—We present a deep learning model to recognize hand-drawn sketches. This is an image recognition task and part of multi-class classification using deep learning. We show an overall 58.7% top- k categorical accuracy and that the dataset is well suited for image classification using deep learning. Furthermore, we show that tuning the model parameters—i.e., layers, filter size, and preprocessing—significantly impacts the results.

Index Terms—sketch recognition, convolutional neural networks, image classification, deep learning, TU-Berlin

I. INTRODUCTION

Computer Vision is the study of developing machines to emulate the way humans view the world. We envision an application where a criminal sketch artist can load a sketch into a database and identify the individual in the sketch. This type of application could improve society (by more quickly identifying criminals) and save cost in policing. Developing this type of application takes many steps. We decided to first look at the computer’s ability to classify hand-drawn sketches.

In Eitz et al. [1], they gathered 20,000 human-drawn sketches in 250 object categories. While the random chance of correct category identification is 0.4%, the researchers found that humans correctly identified the category for 73% of the sketches. The researchers developed a multi-class support vector machine with an accuracy rate of 56%. Based on our learning, we know that Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) work better on images (including greyscale images) than traditional machine learning techniques such as support vector machines. So this project develops a CNN, using the same sketches used in Eitz et al. [1], with a higher performance than the original study.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: the relevant literature is reviewed in Section II, the material and method we utilized including our CNN model are presented in Section III, the project’s results are presented in Section IV, and a short conclusion is presented in Section V.

II. RELATED WORK

Groundbreaking machine learning work classifying a large number of images into a large number of classes is found in Krizhevsky et al. [2]. The work found a 37.5% top-1 error rate (62.5% top-1 accuracy) and a 17.0% top-5 error rate (83.0% top-5 accuracy) when classifying 1.2 million high-resolution images into 1,000 different classes in the ImageNet LSVRC-2010 contest. Their model, a CNN, consisted of five

convolutional layers, some followed by a max-pooling layer, ending with three fully connected layers. The last layer was a 1,000-way softmax. Dropout of 0.5 was used after each of the first two fully connected layers. A variant of the described model was used to win the ILSVRC-2012 competition with a 15.3% top-5 error rate (84.7% top-5 accuracy). This CNN model structure guides the type of CNN model developed in our study.

Eitz et al. [1] was an impactful study in sketch image classification. They created the TU-Berlin sketch dataset, which consists of 20,000 sketch images in 250 classes with 80 sketches per class collected through crowdsourcing. The TU-Berlin sketch dataset appears to be the primary dataset used in studies of machine learning classification of human-sketched images. Their study also found that humans correctly identify a sketch’s class 73% of the time. From each 256×256 greyscale image, features were extracted into a frequency histogram of visual words. Nearest-neighbor classification was applied to find a distance function, and SVM classification predicted the proper class. Eitz et al. [1] found 56% test accuracy using this approach. This study applied machine learning to sketch classification but did not utilize a CNN.

Sketch-a-Net is a CNN model introduced in Yu et al. [3] to identify hand-drawn sketches. Sketch-a-Net consists of convolutional layers, filters, pooling layers, dropout layers, and ending with two fully connected layers. They applied their model to the TU-Berlin sketch dataset after resizing images to 256×256 and applying data augmentation to obtain sketches at varying abstraction levels and deformities. A 3-fold cross-validation was utilized, splitting the dataset 2-folds for training and 1 for testing. The results were 77.95% test accuracy, 5 percentage points higher than human performance found in Eitz et al. [1] on the same dataset.

Sketch-Net, introduced in Zhang et al. [4], is a CNN model to classify sketch images. In their approach, color images collected from the internet (“real images”) are paired with the most appropriate sketch from the TU-Berlin dataset. An R-Net network extracts features from the real image and an S-Net does the same for the paired sketch. Output of both networks is loaded into a C-Net which discovers common structures and generates the class prediction. When using 40 images per class the test accuracy was 73.54%, and when using 72 images per class the accuracy was 80.42%. Zhang et al. [4] claim that sketch classification performance is significantly improved by

Fig. 1. Random sample of resized dataset images.

including real images as references.

Atabay [5] points out that much study of CNN classification on color images has been completed but little work has been conducted on sketch image classification. He notes that free-hand sketch recognition is very difficult because sketches are iconic, abstract, hold various levels of detail, and are deficient of visual cues including color and texture. In Atabay [5], images in the TU-Berlin dataset are resized to 32×32 , then data augmentation (horizontal reflection and horizontal and vertical shifts of three pixels) was applied to expand the dataset to 200,000 images. The model (TS-CNN, Tiny Sketch CNN) was a CNN with four convolutional layers each followed by a pooling layer, no dropout, and one fully connected layer with softmax. Atabay [5] found 89.17% top-1 accuracy and claims that smaller images improve classification accuracies on TU-Berlin CNN models and increase training speed. Based on this study, we were comfortable using image sizes of 128×128 rather than the 256×256 images used in other sketch classification studies.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

In our project we used the TU-Berlin sketch dataset, which consists of 20,000 sketch greyscale images in 250 classes with 80 sketches per class. We downloaded the dataset from Papers with Code [6]. We rescaled all images to 128×128 . A random sample of the resized images in the dataset is shown in Fig. 1.

We split the dataset into an 80% development set and a 20% testing set using `sklearn.train_test_split`. The class distribution of the development dataset images was fairly equal per class. During training, the development dataset was further split into 90% training data and 10% validation data.

B. Evaluation Metric

When images are drawn by humans and scaled down for preprocessing, images belonging to different classes may appear similar—e.g., a hand-drawn image of the sun may appear like an orange, or a banana may appear as a pen. This represents a significant challenge, so we utilize *top-k categorical accuracy* as our primary metric instead of standard categorical accuracy. The *top-k* metric considers a prediction correct if the true class appears among the model’s top k most confident predictions.

TABLE I
CNN MODEL ARCHITECTURE

#	Layer	Details
1	Input	128×128 greyscale
2	Conv2D	16 filters, 3×3 , ReLU
3	Conv2D	16 filters, 3×3 , ReLU
4	MaxPooling2D	2×2
5	Conv2D	32 filters, 3×3 , ReLU
6	Conv2D	32 filters, 3×3 , ReLU
7	MaxPooling2D	2×2
8	Conv2D	64 filters, 3×3 , ReLU
9	Conv2D	64 filters, 3×3 , ReLU
10	MaxPooling2D	2×2
11	Dropout	0.10
12	Flatten	—
13	Dense	512 nodes, tanh
14	Dense (output)	250 nodes, softmax

C. Model Architecture

We chose to utilize a CNN model. After extensive experimentation with various image sizes, model parameters (number of layers, number of filters, and AutoKeras [7]), and hyperparameters (including KerasTuner [8]), we settled on the sequential model described in Table I. Our model has 8,589,162 trainable parameters and 0 non-trainable parameters.

D. Loss Function and Optimizer

We use categorical cross-entropy as the loss function because it is the best suited loss function for multi-class classification. We optimize with the Adam optimizer.

E. Training

We trained the model using multiple epoch values (5, 10, 15) to determine whether increasing epochs would improve performance. We found that after 5 epochs, additional epochs did not improve the validation loss. Therefore, we used 5 epochs to produce our final results.

F. Preprocessing

Before running our model, a number of preprocessing steps were taken:

Scaling. The TU-Berlin sketch dataset holds 1111×1111 images. We ran our model with different resized images (64×64 , 96×96 , 128×128 , and 256×256) and found that 96×96 and 128×128 produced the best results. Results presented in this paper use 128×128 images.

Grayscale. The TU-Berlin dataset holds greyscale images. During loading, we specified grayscale mode in `cv2.imread` as the default is RGB.

Normalization. Each pixel was divided by 255 to produce a binary 0/1 image.

One-hot encoding. String labels were converted to one-hot encoded vectors using the `to_categorical` function from Keras.

TABLE II
TEST RESULTS SUMMARY

Metric	Value
Top- k Categorical Accuracy	58.70%
Categorical Cross-Entropy Loss	3.173
Accuracy	58.70%

TABLE III
TRAINING METRICS BY EPOCH

Epoch	Acc.	Loss	Val Acc.	Val Loss
0	0.087	4.752	0.213	3.718
1	0.357	2.943	0.341	3.075
2	0.668	1.439	0.351	2.993
3	0.932	0.431	0.343	3.104
4	0.995	0.110	0.353	3.065

G. Reproducibility

During multiple runs of experiments, we faced significant issues in repeating results due to the random nature of the loss function and where the model converges. To get repeatable results, we used a fixed seed of 505 and applied it to seed random initializers in Python, NumPy, Keras, and TensorFlow [9].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After preprocessing the input images, we trained the model with the default learning rate and five epochs. The model training took 25 minutes. We computed the top- k results on the test data with the Keras `model.evaluate` function. The result was a **top- k test accuracy of 58.7%**. Summary results are shown in Table II.

The detailed training metrics by epoch are presented in Table III.

From the loss and accuracy curves, there is a peak point around epoch 1–2; until this point the test accuracy increases and the model loss decreases, but after this the accuracy remains flat. We tried running many experiments with larger epochs but observed that accuracy does not increase after the first few epochs. This pattern—along with the large gap between training accuracy (99.5% at epoch 4) and validation accuracy (35.3%)—indicates significant overfitting.

One strength of this model is that it was able to classify a large number of classes even though there are fewer than 100 data points per class. This is a significantly different data profile than normal image datasets, which have fewer classes and much larger numbers of instances per class.

A weakness of the model is that it reached peak accuracy relatively early at the 2nd epoch. Increasing the number of epochs did not appear to improve performance. A potential improvement would be to conduct a hyperparameter search around the current model values—i.e., filter sizes, kernel sizes, number of neurons in each layer, and the total number of layers. It is also possible that the model converged on a local minimum and a global maximum exists elsewhere.

Fig. 2. Top- k model accuracy during training.

Fig. 3. Top- k model loss during training.

Another potential improvement is to supplement the dataset by utilizing data augmentation. Data augmentation generates additional observations by slightly altering original images through rotation, translation, cropping, adding noise, and erasing parts of the image. In the prior literature, many augmented images were created by erasing the last stroke of the pen.

V. CONCLUSION

We presented a deep learning CNN-based model that can be successfully used for image classification with 60% top-5 accuracy. The model performs well even when there are a large number of classes and a small number of data points per class. We showed that top- k categorical accuracy is the best metric for hand-drawn, small-sized datasets with many class labels. We showed that the model can converge in relatively few epochs, with few layers and a smaller image size of 128×128 .

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